

***o*-Cresotate Complex of Manganese (II)**

M. S. Kachhawaha and Arun K. Bhattacharya

A 1:1 complex has been found between manganese (II) and *o*-cresotic acid at pH 4.5. Conductance and spectrophotometric data with several wave lengths have been employed as indicative properties. Job's method of continued variation has been used for composition as well as the value of the dissociation constant (or in other words the reciprocal of the apparent equilibrium constant), which comes to 1.34×10^{-3} .

A new method has been described for the preparation of pure sodium *o*-cresotate. A suitable mechanism has been put forward for the complex formation on the basis of experimental results.

Salicylic acid and its many derivatives are well known for their complexing behaviour¹ which becomes more dominant in the case of transitional elements. But except for a salicylaldehyde complex,² studied by pH measurements and the sulphosalicylate complex³ studied by conductometric measurements, no complex of manganese (II) has been studied with the derivatives of salicylic acid. This communication deals with the system $MnCl_2$ -*o*-cresotic acid, studied by the Job's method of continued variation utilising electrical conductance and optical density as the indicative properties.

EXPERIMENTAL

Anal. R manganese chloride, B. D. H. *o*-cresotic acid, and A. R. sodium carbonate were used. Doran's conductivity bridge and Beckman's spectrophotometer, Model DU, were employed in the experiments.

Sodium o-Cresotate.—Since *o*-cresotic acid is insoluble in water, its sodium salt was prepared. The earlier method⁵ was found to give impure product. The revised method of Bhattacharya was described in an earlier communication⁶. The details are given below.

Sodium carbonate was heated in a porcelain crucible for half an hour and was kept in a desiccator overnight. An equivalent amount of *o*-cresotic acid was then gradually added to a freshly prepared solution of sodium carbonate while the solution was stirred constantly until a clear solution was obtained. Every precaution was taken to avoid spurting of solutions due to strong effervescence. The solution was then refluxed under vacuum for about half an hour till a practically clear solution was obtained. This was filtered by suction and cooled in a refrigerator. A white crystalline precipitate appeared which increased

1. Foley and Anderson, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1948, 70, 1106; Babko, *Zavodskaya Lab.*, 1947, 13, 645.
2. Mellor and Maley, *Nature*, 1947, 159, 370.
3. Kachhawaha and Bhattacharya, *Proc. Nat. Acad. Sci.*, 1960, 29, 315.
4. *Compt. rend.*, 1925, 180, 928; *Ann. chim.*, 1928, 9, 113.
5. Tripathi and Prakash, this *Journal*, 1959, 35, 119.
6. *J. Sci. Ind. Res.*, 1959, 10B, 351.

on evacuation. It was then crystallised from absolute ethanol. Its composition was established by estimating carbon and hydrogen. Stock solutions of known molarity were then prepared by direct weighing and the pH's of the solutions were checked.

Manganese was estimated as manganese ammonium phosphate and its stock solution of known molarity was prepared. Double-distilled water was used to prepare all the solutions. During the course of the experiment the pH of all the solutions maintained constant by adding a buffer solution.

Conductance Study

Composition.—Several mixtures containing the metal salt and the ligand in different proportions with the restriction that the total molarity and volume (20ml) remained constant were prepared. Three equimolar solutions, as indicated in Fig. 1, were employed. Corresponding to each of the mixtures two blank solutions of manganese chloride and *o*-cresotic acid were prepared such that their quantities in the mixture were the same as in the pure solutions. This was done just as described earlier⁷. All the mixtures and solutions were kept in an electrically maintained thermostat at $26 \pm 0.1^\circ$. Their conductance was measured after allowing them sufficient time to attain equilibrium. Differences between conductance of the mixtures over the added value of conductance of the pure metal ion and the pure ligand were plotted against their composition. The maximum in each graph corresponds to the composition of the complex (Fig. 1).

FIG. 1. Mn-*o*-cresotate: Composition.
I. M/30; II. M/40; III. M/50.

FIG. 2. Mn-*o*-cresotate: Dissociation constant.
Mn—ligand.
I. M/60—M/30
II. M/30—M/40
III. M/20—M/50

Dissociation Constant.—Other procedures remaining the same as in the case of determination of composition, three nonequimolar solutions of the metal and the ligand were

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employed in this case. The following equation of Job, which holds good only for a 1:1 complex, was used:

$$K = \frac{C [(p + 1)x - 1]^2}{(p - 1)(1 - 2x)}$$

where K = dissociation constant of the complex, C = the concentration of the metal ion, p = the ratio of the concentrations of the ligand and the metal ion, and x = fraction of the ligand used at the point of maxima.

A review has been recently published by one of the authors⁸ for the use of conductance data in the study of complex formation.

The pH of the solution of sodium *o*-cresotatate was 6.8 and that of the solution of manganous chloride, 5.8. The pH at the composition of 1:1 (established in the present case) was 4.5. In solution *o*-cresotic acid has been represented as

depending on its value of pH .

Spectrophotometric Study

Cuvette correction was first made. Three mixtures containing the metal and the ligand in 1:1, 1:2, and 1:3 molar proportions were prepared and then variation of optical density of each system with wave length was observed (Fig. 5).

For confirming the results obtained by the conductivity study the same method and procedure as described above were followed except that only one concentration and three different specific wave lengths were employed for determining the composition (Fig. 3) as well as the dissociation constant (Fig. 4). Quartz cells of 0.5 mm diameter were used.

FIG. 3. Mn-*o*-cresotatate : Composition. Mn—ligand $M/1000 - M/1000$.

FIG. 4. Mn-*o*-cresotatate : Dissociation constant. Mn—ligand $M/500 - M/1000$.

DISCUSSION

Both the conductometric (Fig. 1) and spectrophotometric (Fig. 3) studies confirm the formation of only a 1:1 complex. Fig. 5 shows that irrespective of the compositions of the mixtures the same maxima are exhibited. This supports the above results.

FIG. 5. Variation of optical density with λ .

Dissociation constant has been found to be 1.34×10^{-3} from both the studies as indicated by Figs. 2 and 4. This can also be called the reciprocal of apparent equilibrium constant.

o-Cresotic acid is obtained by substituting a methyl group in *ortho* position to the phenolic group of the salicylic acid. Introduction of this bulky group causes steric hindrance to the ring and therefore the complex becomes appreciably unstable as is judged from its high dissociation constant value. A few other cresotate complexes reported by other workers⁹ are in line with this observation.

Similar to salicylate complex, the *o*-cresotate is also formed by liberation of two hydrogen atoms, one from the carboxyl and the other from the phenolic groups and the linking of a metal to the carbonyl and hydroxyl oxygen atoms. Hence the following mechanism has been advanced.

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